
The Influence of Shopping Lifestyle, Fashion Involvement on Impulse Buying Behavior with Brand Trust as an Intervening Variable

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Abstract: Fashion has seamlessly integrated itself into the lifestyle of individuals. Manufacturers need to pay attention to consumer behavior because this behavior is often related to impulsive buying. This research aims to determine whether there is an influence of shopping lifestyle and fashion involvement on impulse buying behavior of H&M customers in Manado Town Square, either simultaneously or partially. This research is a case study research with a research method, namely a quantitative method. The data sources used in the research are primary data and secondary data. This research was conducted at H&M Manado Town Square. The research respondents were 100 people (sample determination using non-probability sampling techniques with purposive sampling method). Data was collected using a questionnaire and analyzed using validity tests, reliability tests and multiple linear regression using SPSS 27 for Windows. The results of this analysis conclude that 1) Shopping Lifestyle has a significant influence on Impulse Buying Behavior 2) Fashion Involvement has a significant influence on Impulse Buying Behavior 3) Brand Trust has a significant influence on Impulse Buying Behavior 4) Shopping Lifestyle and Fashion Involvement simultaneously have a significant influence on the Impulse Buying Behavior of H&M Manado Town Square customers.

Key words: Shopping Lifestyle, Fashion Involvement, Brand Trust, Impulse Buying Behavior.

INTRODUCTION

Background

In the fashion industry, impulse buying behavior is a frequent phenomenon. Shopping lifestyle and involvement in fashion are often the main triggers for this behavior. However, brand trust is also thought to play an important role in mediating this relationship. Shopping Lifestyle refers to an individual's behavioral patterns and preferences in shopping activities, which reflect their values, interests and activities. These factors often determine how and how often a person makes purchases, including the tendency to make impulse purchases. Fashion Involvement is the level of interest and attention an individual gives to fashion and fashion trends. High involvement in fashion can encourage more active and frequent purchasing behavior, including impulse purchases. Impulse Buying Behavior describes the act of buying spontaneously and without prior planning, often triggered by emotional or situational impulses. Brand Trust: The level of consumer trust in a particular brand, which can influence purchasing decisions and consumer loyalty. Brand trust is considered to be able to mediate the relationship between shopping lifestyle, fashion involvement, and impulse buying behavior.

Research purposes

This research aims to:

1. Knowing the direct influence of shopping lifestyle and fashion involvement on impulse buying behavior.
2. Examining the role of brand trust as an intervening variable that can strengthen or weaken the influence of shopping lifestyle and fashion involvement on impulse buying behavior.

The purposes of this research are multifaceted, aiming to provide a comprehensive understanding of how shopping lifestyle and fashion involvement influence impulse buying behavior, with brand trust playing an intervening role. The specific purposes of this study include:

1. To Investigate the Influence of Shopping Lifestyle on Impulse Buying Behavior. Examine how various aspects of shopping lifestyle, such as frequency of shopping, preferences for online or offline shopping, and social influences, impact consumers' tendency to make impulse purchases.
2. To Analyze the Impact of Fashion Involvement on Impulse Buying Behavior. Explore the extent to which consumers' interest in and engagement with fashion trends, brands, and products contribute to spontaneous purchasing decisions.
3. To Assess the Role of Brand Trust as an Intervening Variable. Determine whether and how brand trust mediates the relationship between shopping lifestyle and impulse buying behavior. Evaluate the mediating effect of brand trust in the relationship between fashion involvement and impulse buying behavior.
4. To Provide Insights for Marketing Strategies. Offer practical implications for marketers and retailers on how to leverage shopping lifestyle and fashion involvement to enhance impulse buying behavior. Suggest strategies to build and maintain brand trust to strengthen consumer loyalty and encourage impulse purchases.
5. To Contribute to Academic Literature. Add to the existing body of knowledge on consumer behavior by integrating the concepts of shopping lifestyle, fashion involvement, and brand trust. Provide empirical evidence through quantitative analysis to support or challenge existing theories related to impulse buying behavior.
6. To Develop a Conceptual Framework. Propose a comprehensive model that illustrates the relationships among shopping lifestyle, fashion involvement, brand trust, and impulse buying behavior. Test the proposed model using path analysis to validate the hypothesized relationships and understand the dynamics among these variables.

LITERATURE REVIEWS

Theories used in research

1. Consumer Behavior Theory Consumer Behavior Theory. Kotler & Keller (2016): States that consumer behavior is influenced by cultural, social, personal and psychological factors. Schiffman & Kanuk (2010): Explain that the consumer decision-making process involves several stages, starting from need recognition to post-purchase evaluation. This theory can be used to understand how shopping lifestyle influences impulse buying behavior. For example, consumers with certain shopping lifestyles may be more prone to impulse buying due to cultural and social influences that encourage them to shop frequently.
2. Involvement Theory (Zaichkowsky, 1985) – States that involvement is the level of personal importance and relevance that a person feels towards an object (product, activity, or decision). Engagement levels can be divided into high and low engagement. High involvement is usually associated with products that have high emotional and symbolic value for consumers.
3. Fashion involvement is an application of involvement theory where high involvement in fashion can influence impulse buying behavior. Consumers who are highly interested in fashion may make more frequent impulse purchases when they see products that match their interests and fashion trends.

4. Brand Trust Theory (Delgado-Ballester & Munuera-Aleman, 2001). Brand trust is consumers' belief that a brand is reliable and fulfills its promises. This trust is built through positive experiences with the brand, consistent communication, and satisfactory product quality. Brand trust as an intervening variable in this research can explain how trust in brands strengthens the relationship between shopping lifestyle and fashion involvement with impulse buying behavior. For example, consumers who trust a brand may be quicker to make impulse purchases due to the belief that the product will meet their expectations.
5. Impulse Buying Theory (Rook, 1987) explains that impulse buying is a purchase made without prior planning, often driven by a sudden and strong impulse. Situational and emotional factors, such as consumer mood and shopping environment, greatly influence this behavior. This theory helps in understanding how shopping lifestyle and fashion involvement can trigger impulse buying behavior. Consumers with a lifestyle of more frequent shopping and high involvement in fashion may experience the urge to buy impulsively more often.

Research Model and Hypothesis

Research Model

Figure 1. Research Model

Sumber: Literature Reviews, 2024

Hypothesis

H1: It is suspected that shopping lifestyle and fashion influence influence Impulse Buying Behavior

H2: It is suspected that shopping lifestyle influences Impulse Buying Behavior

H3: It is suspected that Fashion Involvement influences Impulse Buying Behavior

H4: It is suspected that Shopping Lifestyle has an influence on Brand Trust

H5: It is suspected that Fashion Involvement has an influence on Brand Trust

H6: It is suspected that Brand Trust has an influence on Impulse Buying Behavior

RESEARCH METHODS

The research approach method used in this research quantitative approach.

Location and Place of Research

Research Location at the H&M store in Manado Town Square

Metode of Collecting Data

1. Questionnaire. Questionnaire is a data collection technique that is carried out by giving a set of written statements or questions to respondents to answer them (Sugiyono, 2014).
2. Documentation. Documentation is a way to obtain data directly from the research site. With this documentation technique, researchers can obtain information not from sources, but they obtain information from various other written sources or from documents available to informants in the form of documents.

Populasi dan Sampel Penelitian

Research Population and Sample

The population considered is consumers who have made purchases in stores H&M Brand located in Manado Town Square. However, because H&M consumer data cannot be known and reached, researchers used non-probability sampling techniques. This research focuses on consumers who spontaneously shop at H&M Manado Town Square without any prior planning. For this research, a non-probability sampling technique is used.. sampling.. A non-probability technique is a sampling technique that does not provide the same chance or opportunity as the sample. Ferdinand (2006), states that if the sample size is large and changes change to be very sensitive so it is difficult to get a good goodness of fit.

Data analysis

The data that has been analyzed is 100 samples.

Research Instrument

In the field of research, there are various tools and instruments that researchers use to collect data. These instruments include various measuring tools including tests, questionnaires, initial guidelines and observation guidelines (Sugiyono, 2019). One particular instrument, known as the Likert scale, is commonly used to measure attitudes, opinions, and perceptions of individuals or groups regarding social phenomena. This scale consists of questions that offer respondents five different options, as illustrated in the table below (Sugiyono, 2019).

Table 1. Likert Measurement Scale

Question	Weight
1. Strongly agree/Very Correct	5
2. Agree/Correct	4
3. Neutral	3
4. Somewhat disagree	2
5. Disagree	1

Source: Sugiyono, 2019

RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Research result

Validity test (Error Test) is a tool used to measure whether a questionnaire is valid/valid. The criteria used are valid or invalid if:

If $r_{count} > r_{table}$ or $sig < 0.05$, then the statement item is valid

If $r_{count} < r_{table}$ or $sig > 0.05$, then the statement item is invalid

Table 2. Validity Test Results

Variable	Indicator	r count	r table	Significant	α	description
Shopping Lifestyle (X1)	X1.1	0,748	0,1654	< 0,001	0,05	Valid
	X1.2	0,781	0,1654	< 0,001	0,05	Valid
	X1.3	0,757	0,1654	< 0,001	0,05	Valid
	X1.4	0,713	0,1654	< 0,001	0,05	Valid
	X1.5	0,721	0,1654	< 0,001	0,05	Valid
	X1.6	0,658	0,1654	< 0,001	0,05	Valid
	X1.7	0,549	0,1654	< 0,001	0,05	Valid
Fashion Involvement (X2)	X2.1	0,699	0,1654	< 0,001	0,05	Valid
	X2.2	0,757	0,1654	< 0,001	0,05	Valid
	X2.3	0,665	0,1654	< 0,001	0,05	Valid
	X2.4	0,757	0,1654	< 0,001	0,05	Valid
	X2.5	0,730	0,1654	< 0,001	0,05	Valid
	X2.6	0,616	0,1654	< 0,001	0,05	Valid
	X2.7	0,564	0,1654	< 0,001	0,05	Valid
Impulse Buying (Y)	Y.1	0,471	0,1654	< 0,001	0,05	Valid
	Y.2	0,741	0,1654	< 0,001	0,05	Valid
	Y.3	0,837	0,1654	< 0,001	0,05	Valid
	Y.4	0,782	0,1654	< 0,001	0,05	Valid
	Y.5	0,794	0,1654	< 0,001	0,05	Valid
	Y.6	0,854	0,1654	< 0,001	0,05	Valid
	Y.7	0,661	0,1654	< 0,001	0,05	Valid

Source: SPSS Data Processing Results 27, 2024

Based on the validity test results table above, it shows that all statement items have a calculated r value > r table or sig < 0.05, so it can be concluded that all statement items are valid.

Reliability Test

Reliability testing is a tool for measuring a questionnaire which is an indicator of a variable or construct. This reliability test was carried out to test the consistency of respondents' answers through the statements given, using the Cronbach Alpha statistical method with the following significance:

If the Cronbach's alpha value is > 0.60, then the variable is reliable

If the Cronbach's alpha value is <0.60, then the variable is not reliable

Table 3. Reliability Test Results

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	Standard	Description
Shopping Lifestyle (X1)	0,833	0,60	Reliabel
Fashion Involvement (X2)	0,809	0,60	Reliabel
Impulse Buying (Y)	0,865	0,60	Reliabel

Source: SPSS Data Processing Results 27, 2024

Based on the reliability test results table above, it shows that all variables have a Cronbach's alpha value > 0.60, which means it is greater than the standard value used, namely 0.6. So it can be concluded that all variables are reliable.

Classic assumption test

Normality Test

This research's normality test used the non-parametric Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S) test. In the Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S) test, it is said whether the data is normally distributed or not, namely:

If the sig value is > 0.05, then the data is normally distributed

If the sig value <0.05, then the data is not normally distributed

Table 3. Normality Test Results
One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test

		<i>Unstandardized Residual</i>	
N		100	
<i>Normal Parameters^{a,b}</i>	Mean	.0000000	
	Std. Deviation	3.55458721	
<i>Most Extreme Differences</i>	Absolute	.074	
	Positive	.045	
	Negative	-.074	
<i>Test Statistic</i>		.074	
<i>Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)^c</i>		.200 ^d	
<i>Monte Carlo Sig. (2-tailed)^e</i>	Sig.		.196
	99% Confidence Interval	Lower Bound	.186
		Upper Bound	.206
<p><i>a. Test distribution is Normal.</i> <i>b. Calculated from data.</i> <i>c. Lilliefors Significance Correction.</i> <i>d. This is a lower bound of the true significance.</i> <i>e. Lilliefors' method based on 10000 Monte Carlo samples with starting seed 2000000.</i></p>			

Source: SPSS Data Processing Results 27, 2024

Based on the table of Kolmogorov-Smirnov normality test results above, it shows that the significant value is 0.200 > 0.05, so it can be stated that all data is normally distributed.

Multicollinearity Test

If the tolerance value is > 0.10 or the VIF value is < 10, then it passes the multicollinearity test.

If the tolerance value is <0.10 or the VIF value is > 10, then it does not pass the multicollinearity test.

Table 4. Multicollinearity Test Results

Coefficients^a			
Model		Collinearity Statistics	
		Tolerance	VIF
1	TotalX1	.435	2.297
	TotalX2	.435	2.297

a. Dependent Variable: Total Y

Source: SPSS Data Processing Results 27, 2024

The results of the multicollinearity test show that all variables have a tolerance value > 0.10 or a VIF value < 10, so it can be concluded that there are no symptoms of multicollinearity or have passed the multicollinearity test.

Heteroscedasticity Test

If the sig value is > 0.05, then it passes the heteroscedasticity test

If the sig value is <0.05, then it does not pass the heteroscedasticity test

Tabel 5. Hasil Uji Heteroskedastisitas (Glejser)

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	3.550	1.462		2.429	.017
	TotalX1	-.104	.074	-.214	-1.406	.163
	TotalX2	.069	.078	.135	.886	.378

a. Dependent Variable:
Source: SPSS Data Processing Results 27, 2024

The results of the heteroscedasticity test show that all variables have a sig value > 0.05, so it can be concluded that there are no symptoms of heteroscedasticity or have passed the heteroscedasticity test.

Figure 2. Scatterplot

Source: SPSS Data Processing Results 27, 2024

There is no clear pattern and the data distribution spreads above and below or around the number 0, so it can be concluded that the data does not have symptoms of heteroscedasticity or the assumptions of the heteroscedasticity test have been fulfilled.

Discussion

In this research, the indicators studied were 13 indicators, namely: 3 shopping lifestyle variables, 5 fashion involvement indicators, and 5 impulse buying variables. Furthermore, from the sample size range of 5-10, the sample size chosen was 5. Based on the explanation above, the number of samples in this study was determined using the formula:

$$n = \text{Number of indicators} \times 5$$

$$n = 13 \times 5$$

$$= 65 \text{ which is rounded to } 100$$

Thus, the number of samples in this research was 100 consumers of H&M Manado Town Square. The sampling technique used was purposive sampling. The sample criteria for this research are as follows:

1. The customer has purchased goods at the H&M store located in Manado Town Square.
2. Respondents are aged 22-40 years and have an income.
3. This research focuses on consumers who spontaneously shop at H&M Manado Town Square without any prior planning.

Conclusion

Based on the data that has been collected and the tests that have been carried out on the problem, it can be concluded as follows

1. Simultaneously, the variables Shopping Lifestyle (X1) and Fashion Involvement (X2) influence Impulse Buying Behavior (Y). That the calculated F value of 88,717 is greater than the F table value of 3.09019 and the significance value is 0.0000 smaller.
2. Partially Shopping Lifestyle has a positive and significant effect on Impulse Buying Behavior. This is because the calculated t value of the Shopping Lifestyle (X1) variable is 6.339 which is greater than the t table value, namely 1.98447 with a significance level of $0.000 < 0.05$, the higher the Shopping Lifestyle (X1), the higher the Impulse Buying (Y).
3. Partially, Fashion Involvement has a positive and significant effect on Impulse Buying Behavior. This is because the calculated t value of the Fashion Involvement (X2) variable is 2,967 which is greater than the t table value, namely 1.98447 and the significance value is $0.004 < 0.05$, , meaning that the higher the Fashion Involvement (X2), the higher the Impulse Buying (Y).

Suggestion

In the research conducted, the results showed that the variables shopping lifestyle and fashion involvement had a significant effect on impulse buying behavior among H&M visitors in Manado Town Square. With the large number of consumers who have lifestyles and characteristics that are big on the world of fashion and encourage impulse buying, the author advises H&M to maintain product quality and product prices, which means the prices given are in accordance with product quality. Moreover, now many well-known brands have emerged with the latest quality and models, making H&M have to always follow changes in consumer lifestyles to be able to retain consumers and the expected target market.

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